

Assessment of Indiscipline Behaviours among Public Primary Schools Pupils in Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The arts of indiscipline behaviours and unimaginable acts of deviat are prevalent among public primary school pupils in Nigeria. This study examines the issue of indiscipline behaviour among pupils of the upper of public primary schools. The primary purpose was to investigate the act of discipline behaviours among the pupils and the factors causing the indiscipline behaviours. The design for the study was the descriptive research design. The population covers all head teachers, male and female teachers in Delta State public primary school. The sample size of the study was 200 respondent purposive and randomly selected among public school head teachers. Data was collected using the questionnaire and open-ended structured statement. The findings revealed various acts/forms of indiscipline behaviours among the pupils to include telling of lies, fighting/bullying, disobedient to teachers among others. The factors responsible for indiscipline behaviours included the home, school system, peer-group and the society. The indiscipline behaviours caused administrative difficulties and challenges to head teachers. There were evidences of indiscipline behaviours among public primary school pupils. It was recommended among others that the family-parents/guardian, classroom teachers and head teachers should be role model and give adequate supervision to the pupils and have a regular parent-teacher association meetings.

Keywords: Primary school, Public primary school, Pupils, Indiscipline Behaviours, Head Teachers.

Introduction

Indiscipline is a progressing vice befalling our schools even in the primary schools. Today students are engaging in some imaginable misconduct and acts of deviant. The concept of indiscipline is seen in different ways by different authors or researcher but all boil down to a social vice bedevilling the society and practiced among children. Indiscipline means lack of discipline, lack of control, lack of proper training unruly behaviour, disobedience and disorder. (Jekayinfa 2013). Indiscipline among primary school for children is becoming a perennial issue for both parents, teachers and even educational administrators in the various ministries of education. There has been a general public concern on the height and rate of indiscipline in schools. Indiscipline as a concept is seen in different ways and interpretations as a noun or adjective. Kamara et. al. (2024) defines indiscipline as a noun which is failure to obey rules and orders a lack of control in the behaviour of a person or group of people. This a situation where people cannot obey rules and lack control of their behaviour. This is very noticeable in our primary schools today. From the school gate, you could notice pupils non-challant behaviour in early attendance to schools, wearing of all sorts of dresses apart from the school uniform and being disobedient. Very noticeable in our primary school today. From the school gate you could notice pupils non-challant behaviour in early attendance to school, wearing of all sort of dresses apart from the school uniform and being disobedient to rules and regulations of the school. Odebode (2019) opined that indiscipline among students in Nigerian schools remained a source of great concern to stake holders in education. According to this indiscipline has some negative damages such as mental, emotional and physical damage in the society.

Indiscipline could simply be seen as lack of or outright disobedient or failure to adhere to laid down rules and regulations. Indiscipline is a deviation from established and accepted standard of behaviour. Indiscipline behaviours is not peculiar to school environment but could be observed in homes and in society too. In educational environment like school indiscipline behaviours could be described as a violation of school rules and regulations by students/pupils within the school premises. Various forms of indiscipline behaviours common in schools include leaving school without permission, physical aggression, disturbance of others, inappropriate use of school materials and non-compliance with teachers directives as observed by Gyapong & Sabbey (2021). According to Gyapong & Sabbey (2021) Causes of indiscipline behaviours could be factors such as school size, home, individual family, gender, ethnicity z school, societal and peer-group pressure. In a recent study by Kamara *et al* (2024) the cause of indiscipline behaviours among school children were identified as school-based factor, home based factor, learner based factors and societal based factors. Therefore, the issue of indiscipline behaviours among

primary schools pupils particularly in upper classes is evident in our public primary schools. The causes of indiscipline behaviour in upper classes of the primary education level are traceable to the home, school, peer-group and society.

The primary is the next place of education for the child after the home. The school is a microcosm of society, hence the home, school and society influences the child's behaviour. Indiscipline as a concept has been defined by researchers and authors. Adeniye & Adedotun (2019) sees indiscipline lack of discipline, lack of control, lack of proper training. In the view of Enefu et. al. (2019) indiscipline is a behaviour disorder that is tagged an act of delinquency. According to Adejoke and Orekelewa (2020) indiscipline is any act of not conforming to orders, policies, procedures, rules and regulations of the society. In same view, indiscipline could be defined as disobedient to all school rules and regulations; and any act of that is deviant of the accepted behaviours of the school as an educational institution. The child's home, school and society have great influence on the students' behaviour. Infact studies have been carried out extensively on indiscipline and several factors have been identified by scholars. These factors have been traced to the home, school, society and government. Ngirokabuenui (2015) opined that five causes of indiscipline included lack of respect for teachers, teachers lateness to school, family instability, which are evident is lack of training in children. Adegoke and Orekelewa (2020) identified home and societal environments as the major causes of indiscipline in school. For Enefu *et al*, (2015) causes of indiscipline can be found in the school administration and teachers themselves. An earlier study of Ali *et al*, (2014) asserted that school, students and society are the factors responsible for indiscipline in schools. From the above literature, it could be seen that the factors causing indiscipline in schools are the home/family, school, itself the students and the society. Causes of indiscipline in primary schools could include mental factor, family instability, media influences, economic instability, government policies, school leadership and parental attitudes. According to Opara (2020) several factors contribute to indiscipline behaviours which include media influences, environmental factors, inadequate parental upbringing, societal values, negative peer group influencers and lax enforcement school rules and regulations.

In schools today, acts or types of behaviours displayed by children could be grouped into minor, major and intolerable indiscipline behaviours. The minor behaviours were noise-making in class, absenteeism and loitering on school premises. The major indiscipline behaviours were missing classes, habitual lateness, stealing, telling lies, cheating during classes, fellow classmate article like pencils, rulers; while the intolerable indiscipline aits include watching and practicing pornography, rapping school/class mates, vandalism of school property, harassment and drug abuse (Oyem, 2016). Indiscipline is any form of students misbehaviour which students exhibit such as general disobedient constituted authority distraction of school property, poor attitude to learning, abuse of seniority, immoral behaviour, drug abuse, stealing, lateness, truancy, dirtiness and noise making in classroom. According to Ndidiamaka et al (2023) common indiscipline exhibited by primary school pupils are fighting, disobedience, dishonesty, failure of learners to do homework, arrogance, disrespectful to teachers, untidiness, out of seat, non- punctuality, idleness, impolite, distracting others, throwing pens in attentive in the class, lying among others.

Indiscipline which producers behaviour among primary school has some negative effects on the pupils in hindering effective functioning of the school system. Ngirokabuenui, (2015) opined that indiscipline constitutes hitches that inhibit the effective school system in the study carried out by Adeniye and Adedotun, (2019) it was reported that there was a significant difference between indiscipline and academic activities of students and a significant gender difference between discipline and academic activities of students. Enefu *et al* (2019) reported that indiscipline had adverse effects on students' academic performance. Adegoke and Orekelewa, (2020) reported that indiscipline contributed to poor performance of secondary school students. Indiscipline behaviours among children in school has negative consequences on the learners and the school at large.

Indiscipline behaviours among primary school pupils have become a pervasive concern in contemporary educational setting. The increasing incidence of unruly behaviour disobedience and disruptive conduct among school pupils poses significant challenges to effective teaching, learning and school administration. This phenomenon undermines the academic achievement, socialization and emotional well-being of pupils, ultimately jeopardizing their future projects. Indiscipline behaviours among primary school pupils have reached alarming stage. There has been efforts to promote discipline but indiscipline behaviour has continued to manifest through disruptive behaviour of fighting and bullying; disobedience to rules and authority and social misbehaviour such as stealing, lying with all forms of dishonesty and disrespect. Over the years, there has been increasing rate of indiscipline behaviours among primary school pupils in public schools Enefu et al (2019) carried out a research on effects of indiscipline on Academic performance of secondary school students while Adeniyi & Adedolun (2019) studied indiscipline and academic of studies – implications for counselling. This study is an assessment of indiscipline behaviour among public primary school pupils in Delta State with a focus on incidence and factors causing indiscipline behaviour among pupils in public primary schools and its influence on school administration.

Objectives of the study

The general objective was to assess the prevalence and factors causing indiscipline behaviours and the influence on indiscipline behavior on head teacher administration in public primary school. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Assess the types of indiscipline behaviours exhibited by public primary school pupils.
2. Identify the causes of indiscipline behaviours among public primary school pupils.
3. Examine the influence of indiscipline behaviours on the head teacher's school administration.

Research Questions

In this study on the assessment of indiscipline behaviours among primary school pupil answers are sought to the following research questions that guided the study:

1. What are the ratings of indiscipline among pupils in the public primary school by male and female head teacher?
2. What are the factors responsible for the common indiscipline behaviours among pupils of upper classes in public primary schools?
3. How do the indiscipline behaviours of pupils influence your school administration as head teachers?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the ratings of male and female head teachers on the indiscipline behaviours common among pupils of public primary schools.
2. There is no significant difference between the ratings of experienced and less-experienced head teachers on the indiscipline behaviours among pupils of public primary schools.

Methodology

The study was a descriptive research. The study adopted a survey approach. This was to be able to cover a representative sample. The target population of the study comprises of all head teachers in Delta state, using a purposive sample, head teachers were selected from the three senatorial district of the state, from each of the selected schools, head teachers were randomly selected, giving a total of two hundred respondents, composing both male and female Head-Teachers. This represents the population sample for the study. The instrument for the study was a questionnaire developed by the researcher. The instrument has three sections, Section A consists personal data of the respondents, while section B consists list of indiscipline behaviours rating Highly Common (HC), Moderately Common (MC), and Not Common (NC). Section C consists of items of factors responsible for pupils indiscipline behaviors. Respondents were to indicate their choices. The number three research question was an opened ended structured questionnaire the respondents were expected to state how the indiscipline behaviours of the pupils influenced their school administration.

The researcher and trained research assistant administered and collected the questionnaire on the sampled respondents and ensure proper filling and prompt retrieval as they personally administer the questionnaire. Data was analyzed using frequency count, percentage and Chi-Square (X^2) was used to test the formulated hypotheses testing at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Results

Presentation of results on the demographic data of respondents. The three research questions and two hypotheses raised in this study.

Demographic Data of Respondents – Gender

The demographic data of respondents were needed to provide answers to the two hypothesis raised in the study. These were on gender and experience of the respondents.

Table 1: Frequency counts and percentages of respondents based on gender

Variable	Frequency	Percentage %
Male	114	57.0
Female	86	43.0
Total	200	100

Table 1: Showed that male head teachers are 114(57%) while the female head teachers are 86(43%) of the sampled population of respondents.

Table 2: Frequency counts and percentages of respondents based on experience.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage %
Less experienced	80	40.0
Experienced	180	60.0
Total	200	100

Table 2: showed that 120 respondents representing 60% of the total population sample are experienced head teachers while eighty (80) respondents representing 40% of the total sample are less experienced Head Teachers.

Research Question I

What are the ratings of indiscipline behaviours among pupils in public primary school by male and female head teachers?

Table 3: Frequency counts and percentages of respondents' ratings of indiscipline behaviours in among the pupils of public primary school.

S/N	Indiscipline Behaviours	HC	MC	NC	Total
1	Lateness to School	64 (32.0)	91 (45.5)	45 (22.5)	200
2	Talking in the classroom	122(61.0)	71 (35.5)	7 (3.5)	200
3	Neglecting Homework	92(46.0)	90 (45.0)	18 99.0)	200
4	Fighting and Bullying	103(51.0)	82 (41.0)	15(7.5)	200
5	Disobeying the Teacher	173(86.5)	27 (13.5)	-	200
6	Stealing Things	171(85.5)	27 (13.5)	2 (1.0)	200
7	Dishonesty	32(16.0)	86 (43.0)	82 (41.0)	200
8	Sexual Immorality	12(25)	35 (17.0)	154 (75.5)	200
9	Telling Lies	182(90.0)	20 (10.0)	-	200
10	Abusive Language	168(84.0)	29 (14.5)	3 (1.5)	200

HC – Highly common MC- Moderately Common, NC- Not Common

Table 3: shows the frequency counts and percentages of respondents rating of indiscipline behaviours among public primary school pupils. This was presented in the frequency of Highly common (HC) Moderately Common and Not Common (NC).

Table 3 revealed that indiscipline behaviours of telling lies, 182(90.0); destroying teacher 173(86.5), stealing things 171(85.5) Asusive language 168(84.0), taking in the classroom 122(61.0) and fighting and bullying 103(51.0) were highly common among the public primary school pupils.

While lateness to school 91(45.5) and neglecting home work 90(45.0) were moderately common with sexual immorality 154(75.5) was the least of the recorded as no-common indiscipline behaviour among public primary school pupils.

Research Question 2: What are the factors responsible for the common indiscipline behaviours among pupils of in public primary schools?

Table 4: Frequency Count of respondents view on factors responsible for indiscipline behaviours among pupils in public primary schools.

S/N	Family status	School system	Peer pressure	Mass Media	Society	Frequency
1	35	64	78	11	10	200
2	81	17	24	48	30	200
3	10	03	122	60	05	200

Table 6 shows that the calculated Chi square value is less than the T-Value at 0.005 level of significance. This means that the null hypothesis was not rejected. There was a significant difference in the ratings by male and female head teachers.

Hypotheses 2: There is no significant difference between the ratings of experienced and less experienced head teachers on the indiscipline behaviours common among pupils of the public primary schools.

Table 7: Chi- Square analysis of respondents ratings based on the Head Teachers experience.

S/N		HC	MC	N	Total	X ²	DF	Remark
1	LEX	27(25.6)	36(36.4)	17(18.0)	80	0.288	2	NS
	EX	37(38.4)	35(54.6)	28(27.0)				
2	LEX	37(36.8)	37(36.0)	6(7.3)	120	0.31	2	NS
	EX	58(55.2)	53(54.0)	12(10.8)				
3	LEX	2(4.8)	13(13.6)	65(61.6)	80	3.079	2	NS
	EX	16(7.2)	21(20.4)	89(92.4)				
4	LEX	44(41.2)	31(32.8)	5(6.0)	120	0.760	2	NS
	EX	59(61.8)	51(49.2)	10(9.0)				
5	LEX	52(48.8)	25(28.4)	3(2.8)	80	1.052	2	NS
	EX	70(73.2)	46(42.5)	4(4.2)				
6	LEX	63(68.4)	16(10.8)	1(0.8)	120	4.967	2	NS
	EX	108(102.6)	11(16.2)	1(1.2)				
7	LEX	72(72.0)	8(8.0)	-	80	0.000	1	NS
	EX	108(128.0)	17(12.0)					
8	LEX	62(67.2)	117(11.8)	1(1.2)	120	4.916	2	NS
	EX	106(100.8)	12(17.4)	2(1.8)				
9	LEX	67(69.2)	13(10.8)	-	80	0.863	1	NS
	EX	100(103.8)	14(16.2)					
10	LEX	15(12.8)	32(34.4)	33(32.8)	120	0.911	2	NS
	EX	17(19.2)	54(5.6)	49(49.2)				

LEX – less Experienced Head Teachers.

EX = Experienced Head Teachers

HC = Highly Common

MC = Moderately Common

NC = Not Common

Table 7: shows the item analysis of respondents ratings of the indiscipline behaviours among pupils in the upper classes of the public primary schools. The table showed that there was no significant difference based on Head Teachers experience as revealed by the analysis of the responses.

Table 8: Chi square Analysis of overall Average of the respondents response based on experience.

S/N	Experience	Highly Common	Moderately Common	Total	X ²	DF	Remark
1	Less Experienced	33(30.4)	47(49.6)	80	0.031	1	NS
2	Experienced	43(45.6)	77(74.4)	120	0.378		

Table 8 shows that the Chi- Square value is less than the table calculated value at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the ratings of experienced and less experienced head teachers on the levels of indiscipline behaviours among pupils in public primary school is not rejected

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study indicated that the respondent rated telling lies as the highest act of indiscipline among the pupils, others were disobedient to teachers, using abusive language, talking during class, and lateness to school, while sexual immorality was rated the least. The findings agreed with the report of (Oyem, (2016) and Ndidiamaka *et al*, 2023).

On the factors responsible for common indiscipline behavior among public primary school pupils, the respondent agreed that the family, school system, student themselves and society all contributed in the problems of indiscipline behaviours. The findings were in line with the earlier study by Emefu *et al.*, (2015) and Ali *et al.* 2014. Agreeing that the home, school and environment of pupils could influence them. The findings of the study revealed that there was no significant difference between the ratings of indiscipline behaviours among public primary school pupils based on gender. Both male and Female head teachers actually reported the evidence of indiscipline behavior among pupils in public primary school.

The second hypothesis revealed that there was positive but no significant difference between the ratings of less experienced and experienced head teachers on their ratings of discipline behaviours among pupils in public primary schools. Open ended questions were used to solicit head teachers' opinions on how the pupils' indiscipline behavior influenced their school administration. The responses from the head teacher revealed that pupils' indiscipline behavior caused administrative difficulties and challenges such as, Damage to school reputation, compromise of school safety, time consumption – take away valuable time from administrative tasks with increased accountability for indiscipline. Emotional toil brings out stress and burn out affecting the well being of school administrators in public primary schools.

Conclusion

The indiscipline behavior among pupils in upper classes of the primary school is undeniable with pupils engaging in unimaginable misconduct and acts of deviant. There are evidences of indiscipline behaviours among pupils in public primary schools as rated by the head teachers. The factor responsible for indiscipline behaviours included the home, the school, the students, themselves and the society at large. Head teachers are caught in the web of products of indiscipline behavior causing administrative difficulties and challenges in the performance of their school administrative tasks.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. All stakeholders involved in the life of pupils at this tender age; parents, head teachers and class room teachers should task themselves to increase supervision of the children and also to be a role model for the children to imitate for a disciplined behavior.
2. There should be effective head teachers' balance prevention, intervention, and reactive strategies to manage pupils' indiscipline by ensuring conducive, positive learning environment.
3. There should be regular interaction with pupils by showing them empathy and support for pupils.
4. Head teachers should continuously ensure fairness in the discipline of pupils and sometimes allow flexibility approach to suit individual needs of pupils.
5. Advocate for regular Teacher-Parent meeting to discuss pupils' behavior.
6. Lastly, provide counseling service to individual or group counseling for pupils.

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